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California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
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A NEW CLINICAL GUIDELINE: PREVENTION AND TREATMENT OF RECURRENT
URINARY TRACT INFECTION IN SKILLED NURSING

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Due to the high prevalence of Urinary Tract Infections (UTIs), it has become standard practice to prescribe antibiotics to patients with a UTI in Skilled Nursing Facilities (SNF), even if they are asymptomatic. This approach, however, has led to higher rates of antibiotic-resistant conditions. The project systemically examined the effectiveness of clinical measures to prevent and treat recurrent Urinary Tract Infections (rUTIs) among SNF residents. It developed and implemented clinical guidelines to improve the prevention of rUTIs and reduce the rate to less than 5% within three months. In addition, a nurse feedback survey was administered at the end of the study. The aim was to measure nurses' perceptions of the new proposed guideline. The results indicate that the nursing staff perception is positive, given that 85% of participants reported that the proposed guideline was easy to use. The project identifies the value of training staff on revised UTI guidelines. It offers recommendations that will constitute the foundations of a pilot clinical guideline framework that can be used in the SNF setting.

Keywords, recurrent urinary tract infections, Elderly, residents, guideline, skilled nursing

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Background

According to Akhtar et al. (2021) approximately 100,000 hospitalizations due to Urinary Tract Infections (UTIs) occur annually, where 25% of these hospitalizations are among elderly patients due to the complexity of their diagnosis and treatment compared to other populations. Women are more susceptible to UTIs than men because of their unique anatomical structures. Price et al. (2017, p.205) noted that UTI is the most common bacterial infection in adult women, with 50% of women experiencing at least one UTI in their lifetime and as many as 10% having at least one UTI annually. Akhtar et al. (2021, p.1460) indicate that for women aged 65, the prevalence of UTI increases by 10 percent and further increases by 30 percent for women older than 85. An estimated 3% of males in the globe are affected annually by UTIs. In men under 50, the frequency is between five and eight per 10,000 people yearly. However, this study points out that this statistic fails to consider the hospitalized women underdiagnosed (Akhtar et al., 2021, p.1458). One factor influencing increased UTIs in elderly patients, particularly in Skilled Nursing Facilities (SNFs) is indwelling urinary catheters. The presence of an Indwelling catheter can mask signs and symptoms of UTI, antibiotic resistance, and weak immune systems (Aggarawal & Lotfollahzadeh, 2021; Akhtar et al., 2021, p.1458). Recurrent Urinary Tract Infection (rUTI) in older adults is severe and accounts for increased mortality rates, decreased quality of life, antibiotic resistance among geriatric patients, and the excessive economic burden on the healthcare system (Gajdács et al., 2021, p.1).

Treatment, assessment, and prevention guidelines are available in SNFs. However, it appears inconsistent and ineffective in preventing and managing rUTI in this elderly population. Current UTI clinical guidelines entail routine urine testing (Marsh et al., 2019, p.114874) and empirical antimicrobial therapy for UTIs (Smith et al., 2018, p.1174), limiting the use of

appropriate catheter care (Zeng et al., 2020) and cranberry juice or capsule administration (Hudson et al., 2022). However, Zeng and colleagues (2020, p.2709) further note that using cranberry juice or capsules remains controversial. Only now, there is clear evidence in the literature supporting the efficacy and benefits of cranberry juice to prevent or treat UTIs; as a result, it should be included in the guidelines. Additional challenges around rUTI management relate to the controversy about the overuse of antibiotics. UTIs account for many antibiotics prescribed in primary care (Shallcross et al., 2020, p1). Smith et al. (2018 p.1174) reported that women received more antibiotics than men in all age groups, except those >75 years, with women aged 16–54 receiving 36%–40% more antibiotics than men of the same age. However, data suggests that antibiotics are often prescribed inappropriately because of the over-diagnosing of UTIs, especially in the elderly (Shallcross et al., 2020, p1).

Prevalence Rate of rUTI in SNF

UTIs are prevalent among the elderly, with a prevalence rate of 0 to 13.6% annually among females, whereas the lifetime prevalence of UTIs in men is between 13,000 and 14,000 in every 100,000 adult men (Thompson et al., 2020, p91). A UTI is an infection that affects any part of the urinary tract, including the kidneys, ureters, bladder, and urethra. A UTI can be divided into upper and lower urinary tract infections (Wei et al., 2016, p.485). An upper UTI involves the kidneys and ureters, whereas a lower UTI occurs in the bladder and urethra. Depending on the severity of the UTI, it can be further classified as complicated or uncomplicated. Anger et al. (2019, p.282) define a complicated UTI as an infection that infects a person with one risk factor. Therefore, increasing the risks of rUTIs and consequently compromising treatment efficacy. While at the same time, indicated UTI is an infection in an otherwise healthy individual with a standard anatomical and functional urinary tract and has no

risk factors that make them prone to developing UTI (Anger et al., 2019, p.284). Often, patients who experience UTIs are more likely to be re-infected again. A patient having UTIs two or more times within six months or more than three infections within a year is considered to have rUTIs (Storme et al., 2019, p.19; Zeng et al., 2020, p.2709). SNF residents are at higher risk of developing a UTI due to comorbidities such as diabetes, kidney failure, prostate cancer, incontinence, high blood pressure, and hospital-acquired infections (Akhtar et al., 2021, p.1458). These patients can have UTIs that are symptomatic or asymptomatic. Asymptomatic is most common in SNFs (Akhtar et al., 2021, p.1458). Gram-negative bacteria, gram-positive bacteria, and fungi are some microorganisms that cause UTIs (Zhou et al., 2020, p.4730)

Purpose Statement

The overall objective was to identify mechanisms for reducing the rate of rUTI among geriatric residents in SNFs. The proposed intervention involved conducting a systematic literature review and developing clinical guidelines to improve the prevention and treatment of rUTIs in SNF residents. This quality improvement project aims to develop, implement, and evaluate clinical policies to prevent and treat rUTIs among elderly residents in SNFs. Additionally, the project seeks to investigate the staff perception of the new proposed clinical guideline on avoiding and treating rUTIs in elderly residents in SNF settings.

Project Objective

The key objectives were to conduct a systematic literature review to develop clinical guidelines to improve the prevention and treatment of rUTIs in SNF residents; identify staff perception of the new revised clinical guidelines and ; pilot rUTI clinical guidelines for three months to reduce the rate of rUTI to less than 5% within three months.

Supporting Framework

A theoretical framework provides a step-by-step guide to clinical practices using evidence-based research to enhance current policies (Titler et al., 2001, p.497). Incorporating the theoretical framework will help bridge existing information on SNFs practices and UTI risk among elderly residents. The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice (Appendix C) emerged as the most appropriate framework for the current project. The critical factors were the model's purpose, context, and simplicity. The Iowa Model was introduced in 1994 and has since been revised, validated, and adapted with new knowledge. In particular, the framework has been updated to align evidence-based research with clinical practice (Titler et al., 2001, p.497). They further indicated that the model had been utilized by multiple professionals within diverse healthcare settings, hence, validating the model's reliability. This model stipulates that the ten elements are connected; hence, a collaborative effort is vital to achieving QI policies.

The first step of the Iowa Model starts with recognizing triggers for the objective of this DNP project. These triggers can be either knowledge-focused or problem-focused. Based on the Iowa model, these triggers can be an issue identified by the clinic or by the patient. The triggers can also be identified through national, state, or organizational initiatives. They can also emerge from data collected or evidence from a scientific study, a care philosophy, or they are part of rules and regulations from an accrediting company:

- Improper assessment and identification of infection
- Inconsistencies in the use of standardized criteria such as the McGeer guideline
- Lack of adherence to evidence-based protocols by medical providers and staff
- Inconsistent or inadequate hydration program
- Substandard peri-care techniques

Several factors were considered, including the organization's guidelines on the prevention and treatment of rUTIs and the culture of the work setting. The project aimed to identify practical, evidence-based interventions to reduce recurrent UTIs among the elderly over 65 years in SNF. The selected interventions reflected solutions aligned with the current facility's protocols and resources. This project aimed to enhance patient outcomes by reducing UTIs and minimizing healthcare facilities' costs.

Intergration of the Iowa Model into the project (Appendix D) involved deciding whether the problem is a priority to the care facility and stakeholders. rUTIs are a significant concern for residents in care facilities due to the adverse health implications that may increase the risk of death. Moreover, rUTIs have also been found to increase the cost of healthcare. In response to these present realities, the Saskatchewan Infection Prevention and Control Program (2014) stipulates guidelines for patient safety. These can often be broadly interpreted to include strategies to prevent unnecessary rehospitalization. Consequently, care facilities are required to transfer and document incidences of hospitalization and the reason for the transfers from care facilities (SIPCP, 2014).

The standards mandates imposed on medical practice raise concerns about compliance for care facilities. Therefore, besides improving resident outcomes, reducing rUTIs is a priority for care facilities as a strategy to respond to potential compliance challenges. A team was formed upon identifying this initiative's importance to the organization. The project was announced at the clinical leaders, huddle meeting. Subsequently, a group was created based on clinical leadership, technical, and collaborative skills and developed on a volunteer basis. The team included the DNP student, caregivers, nurses, and a primary care provider, a collaborative effort, therefore, premises upon a Specific Measurable Achievable Relevant Timely (SMART) goal.

The SMART goal was to increase nurses' perception of the proposed clinical guideline. The next step was to conduct a systematic literature review to validate the effectiveness of current clinical guidelines and establish new clinical guidelines if needed.

The next phase entailed gathering evidence on minimizing risk factors and comparing current guidelines with the facility's guidelines on treatment measures. The next step would be to identify deficiencies in the current rUTI policy, and a revised policy guideline will be agreed on. The committee members reviewed existing data and discussed the findings at the implementation stage. Suggestions and modifications were agreed upon through a consensus. The committee then proposed a surveillance approach to the proposed guideline to ensure sustainability.

Review of Literature

Overview

A comprehensive review of the literature covering publications from the following databases: PubMed, PsycINFO, CINAHL, and EBSCO was completed for this doctoral project. The search criteria included the following inclusion terms: recurrent urinary tract infections, geriatric patients, long-term care facilities, skilled nursing homes, guidelines for UTIs, and prevention. The search was restricted to current peer-reviewed publications submitted in English between 2017 and 2022. Also, the inclusion/exclusion criteria were guided by the project objectives; thus, articles that did not meet the inclusion criteria were excluded. The original search yielded 67,112 articles. Upon further review, 67,041 were excluded because they focused on hospital settings or reflected weak evidence. The strength of the evidence presented in the articles was assessed using the Johns Hopkins Nursing evidence-based practice models and guidelines (Fencl & Matthews, 2017, p.378). The Johns Hopkins model is a straightforward three-step process that includes identifying the practice question, identifying the best evidence to answer the question, and translating the evidence to practice (Fencl & Matthews, 2017, p.378, p.378). All three forms of evidence were considered in this review, emphasizing evidence literature that focused on solving proof to practice. In sum, 17 articles ultimately met the criteria for the current project.

Clinical Guidelines for Prevention of rUTI in SNF

UTI is the second most prevalent illness in SNF and the most frequent cause of bacterial infection from the GU tract in hospitalization due to communication problems, chronic genitourinary complaints, and other conditions. UTIs occur for many reasons, both acquired and innate. Genetics, antibiotics, spermicides, and sexual activity are a few factors to consider. For

example, fibrinogen, which coats the catheter, may be released when inserted into the urethra and urinary bladder (Klein & Hultgren, 2020, p.221).

For effective prevention and management of rUTI, healthcare providers must thoroughly grasp the underlying causes (Moussa et al., 2020, p.2011). Storme et al. (2019) advocate for tailoring treatment strategies considering the wide range of risk variables that differ from patient to patient. According to a large body of research, estrogen as a prophylactic measure for rUTI was already proven practical Fox et al., (2021). Vaginal estrogen reduces the chances of contracting rUTI, according to a randomly selected control test study conducted by Fox et al.,(2021); however, systemic estrogen did not appear to have the same effect.

Sublingual MV140, developed by Lorenzo-Gómez et al.,(2022) has been presented as a prophylactic measure for rUTIs. Studies have shown insufficient evidence to justify the widespread use of vaccinations to prevent infectious diseases (Aziminia et al., 2018 p.753). Because of the physical changes in the female gastro-urinary system that occur as she ages, she is more likely to have a UTI. Developmental alterations that might harm females tend to involve a loss in bladder rigidity, incontinence, vulvovaginal atrophy, and vaginal prolapse. The decrease in estrogen level resulting from vulvovaginal atrophy might impact the pH level of the vagina and increase the post-residual volume. Those who require assistance in personal care and wearing briefs have an increased risk of infection because of their history of incontinence. It is necessary to change a patient's briefs frequently to prevent infections.

In SNFs, catheterizations are frequently caused by high post-residual volume. Post-residual volume is defined by Ballstaedt and Woodbury (2022) as the quantity of urine remaining in the bladder following an involuntary voiding. The post-residue volume can be employed as a diagnostic tool for many diseases. After voiding, catheterization of the urinary system can obtain

both post-void residue and urine samples. To avoid infection, it is advised that urinary catheterization be done in a sterile environment (Ballstaedt & Woodbury, 2022)

Escherichia coli, typical flora, contains a bacterium that can trigger recurrent urinary tract infectious diseases. Postmenopausal women were also linked to vaginal ailments like bleeding, itching, burning, dyspareunia, and discharge secretion. Dysuria is among the most prominent signs of UTI (Jin, 2017, p.1388). Patients undergoing long-term treatment in SNFs may benefit from medical trends and reconciliation, which could help slow the rate of rUTI among older women (McLellan & Hunstad, 2016, p.946). For years, cranberry juice has been used as a UTI prevention measure. Unfortunately, there is little evidence to back up the usage of cranberry drinks as a preventative measure for rUTIs. In recent research studies, cranberry products include Proanthocyanins found to prevent bacteria from adhering to the urothelium and, as a result, restrict bacterial development (Anger et al., 2019, p282; Aggarwal and Lotfollahzadeh, 2021). Because cranberry tablets are inconsistently formulated, cranberry is best taken as a dietary supplement instead of medicine (Fan et al., 2022). In another study, Bergamin and Kiosoglous (2017) indicated good hygienic practices such as cleaning from the front to the back, washing clothes, utilizing a non-toxic liquid with no perfume or chemicals, appropriate handwashing before wiping the peri section, and avoiding pollutants are essential to infection prevention. Vaginal estrogen should be applied with clean hands to prevent infections (Aggarwal & Lotfollahzadeh, 2021).

Clinical Guidelines for Treatment of rUTI in SNF

Cortes-Penfield et al. (2017) found that clinical outcomes have remained the same after failed attempts to reduce UTIs by coating catheters with antibiotics or cosmetics. As a result, it has pushed up costs and made patients more agitated (Cortes-Penfield et al., 2017). Because of

the increasing incidences of antibiotic-resistant bacteria, treating and managing rUTIs can be difficult for healthcare providers (Nassib et al., 2019). Diagnostic investigations and the precise diagnosis of rUTI are symptoms that are essential for successful therapy (de Ccuetoeet al., 2019, Cortes-Penfield et al., 2017; Storme et al., 2019). The literature shows urine cultures are the best way to diagnose a UTI. Furthermore, leukocyte esterase and nitrate may also be signs of infection (Anger et al., 2019; Aggarwal & Lotfollahezadeh, 2021; Akhtar et al., 2021). To treat UTI, a single dosage of 3 grams of Fosfomycin and 100 mg of Nitrofurantoin is recommended daily; trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole and 800 mg of Trimethoprim (Nassib,2019; Aggarwal & Lotfollahzadeh, 2021).

Treatment of rUTI in elderly patients is, however, challenged by antibiotic resistance. However, antimicrobial prophylaxis can have a long-lasting effect on preventing infections (Anger et al., 2019, p.284). Furthermore, finding out if the bacteria that cause rUTIs are identical or different is critical when dealing with rUTIs. Studies show that six-month antibiotic prophylaxis results in the best outcomes for patients with rUTI (Aggarwal & Lotfollahzadeh, 2021).

A urine sample result should help determine the best antibiotic to use. Urine cultures specific to rUTI help discover bacteria resistant to treatment (Aggarwal & Lotfollahzadeh, 2021; Chu & Lowder, 2018). Three components are necessary for the treatment of rUTI. Uropathogenic *Escherichia coli* strains are incredibly diverse, making vaccine creation extremely difficult. It is difficult to tell if such vaccines are a good fit for SNFs because of the age of the women who would receive them. However, more comprehensive immunization studies in older female individuals in institutions are needed.

Drug-drug interactions are critical for healthcare practitioners, particularly during medication reconciliation. It has been suggested that drug-drug interactions are caused by attempts to alleviate the adverse effects of other medications. According to Noor et al. (2019, p.1), polypharmacy, diabetes mellitus, and congestive heart failure are risk factors that increase the susceptibility of UTIs in elderly populations. Drug-drug interaction has been proposed as a cause of UTIs (Noor et al., 2019; Akhtar, 2021). Patients getting treated for rUTI while using other medications should be closely monitored, as dosage adjustments may be necessary (Noor et al., 2019, p.4).

Guideline Development

Current UTI Guidelines

The McGeer criteria (Appendix A) is the current UTI guideline used by the facility. The guideline directs clinicians on diagnosing UTI, consequently determining patient treatment options based on urinalysis results (Cooper et al., 2021). The McGeer infection surveillance (McGeer et al, 1991)was initially developed in 1991 and updated in 2012 and was specifically to be used by Long Term Care facilities (LTCF) (Stone et al., 2012). UTI signs and symptoms are assessed based on Patients (1) without a catheter, and (2) with indwelling catheters. The guideline is based on urine culture results in addition to the signs and symptoms of the patient. Ultimately, for one to be diagnosed with UTI, at least one sign and symptom should be met. However, two of the localized urinary tract symptoms or signs should be present in the absence of fever or leukocytes. Lastly, one microbiological indicator should also be present (Stone et al., 2012).

Revised Guideline

The current McGeer guideline (McGeer et al, 1991) focuses primarily on assessing whether there is a UTI. However, the guideline does not appear to include preventive measures and the correct collection of urine samples. According to Moussa et al. (2020), clinicians should prioritize preventative measures by investigating the underlying causes of UTIs. Risk factors differ from patient to patient; therefore, the need to personalize preventative and treatment options for patients (Moussa et al., 2020).

To address the shortcomings of the McGeer protocol (McGeer et al, 1991), the proposed guideline (Appendix B) incorporated three preventative measures that seemed to be missing, namely, (1) hydration, (2) hygiene, and (3) catheter management. According to Lean et al. (2019), dehydration has been correlated with high incidences of UTI, especially in the elderly population living in LTCFs. Improving hydration in this population has been seen to improve UTI prevalence rate and, in turn, reduce unnecessary hospitalization due to UTI, not to mention structured hydration rounds in LTCFs is a low-cost intervention measure that could potentially reduce treatment costs (Lean et al., 2019; Scott et al., 2020)

Bergamin and Kiosoglous (2017) indicated good hygienic practices such as cleaning from the front to the back, washing clothes, utilizing a non-toxic liquid with no perfume or chemicals, and appropriate handwashing before wiping the peri section, and avoiding pollutants are essential to infection prevention. Subsequently, to avoid infection, urinary catheterization be done in a sterile environment (Ballstaedt & Woodbury, 2022). Therefore, catheter management is a critical factor in reducing UTI rates in the facility, thus, being incorporated in the proposed guideline. Urine cultures are the standard diagnostic test to confirm UTI (Aggarwal &

Lotfollahzadeh, 2021; Chu & Lowder, 2018). For this reason, proper urine collection technique is essential in establishing proper diagnosis and treatment of UTI.

Methods

The goal of this QI project focused on developing and implementing clinical guidelines designed to prevent and treat rUTIs among elderly residents in a skilled nursing care facility. The objectives were to (a) conduct a systematic literature review to develop a clinical guideline to improve the prevention and treatment of rUTIs in SNF residents, (b) pilot rUTI clinical guidelines for three months to reduce rates of rUTI, and (c) determine staff perception of the proposed clinical guideline. The project design and implementation process was influenced by The Iowa Model, as indicated in Appendix C. Additionally, phone interviews and a survey were utilized to establish staff perception of the proposed guideline and to gather data on rates of UTI over time. The researcher conducted two follow-up contacts to generate maximum response rates.

Project Design

The project design incorporated qualitative and quantitative data collection strategies and included in-person professional development (PD) sessions to assess potential changes in rUTI rates. The PD sessions were offered twice weekly during clinical meetings. These in-person PD sessions took place within the facility's conference room, each lasting 30-40 minutes outside the nurses' regular work duties. At the end of every session, participants sought clarification and offered feedback on the proposed clinical guidelines. Participants were also provided soft and hard copies of the proposed guideline to serve as constant reminders and ensure compliance with the newly developed UTI guideline. The electronic survey was administered at the end of the professional development sessions, and data on UTI rates were obtained.

Setting

The project was implemented at a private SNF in Los Angeles, California. The facility accommodates up to 300 residents and serves Medicare and Medicaid patients. Thus, it is required to comply with Center of Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS) guidelines. The facility utilizes Point click care (PCC), a healthcare software commonly used by LTC facilities. Care providers like Nurse Practitioners can handwrite or type orders directly in PCC. However, all orders must be placed in PCC, whether handwritten or given as a verbal order. Anyone with access to PCC can retrieve patient information. However, access is limited based on user role. For example, clinicians cannot access the administration and financial information. Also, contracted pharmacists can access the patient's medication list and often recommend drugs to continue or discontinue. All orders must be faxed to the pharmacy for verification purposes. The facility's nursing team consists of Registered Nurses (RN), Licensed Vocational Nurses (LVN), and Certified Nurse Assistants (CNA). They all act in distinct roles within their scope of practice.

Participants

Participants in this project were licensed nursing staff in the SNF, including LVNs, RNs, and clinical leaders. CNAs were excluded from the study due to high turnover. The participants in the current study represented a convenience sample of nursing staff. To be included in the sample, participants must have been full-time, part-time, or per-diem and be direct employees of the nesting facility. The nursing staff who were travel nurses or contracted through registries or staffing agencies were excluded from the study.

QI Committee Team and Roles

The QI committee was formed based on individual roles in the facility and their relevance to the central aims of the project. The QI team comprised the DNP student, Director Of Nursing (DON), RNs, LVNs, and Minimum Data Set (MDS) coordinator with a particular focus on clinical leadership roles, technical skills, and collaborative skills related to the goals of the project. In particular, the DON was contributed by managing nursing staff and creating and enforcing compliance with healthcare's current UTI policies. The MDS coordinator oversaw data accuracy in charting, ascertaining that the UTI data rates were adequately tracked. The RNs directly supervised the nursing staff by coordinating care, reporting UTI signs and symptoms, clarifying orders, and liaising with the pharmacist. The LVNs contributed by administering medication, assessing patients, and reporting to care. Overall, the QI team aimed to implement the clinical guideline for treating and preventing UTIs and to reduce the recurrent UTI rates by 5% within three months.

Planning the Quality Improvement Program

In addition to the above mentioned roles, the DON managed nursing employees and created and enforced compliance with the revised UTI guideline. The DNP student assumed a lead role in revising the guideline, providing training, and offering feedback to members of the QI committee as needed. However, committee members made vital decisions and planned collaboratively through consensus. All roles were clearly defined and written down. A step-by-step plan derived from the Iowa Model chaperoned the QI process. rUTI has been an ongoing issue in the facility. The RNs and LVNs verbalized the changes in conditions related to UTI infections. At times they described this task as time-consuming, taking away time that would have otherwise been dedicated to direct patient care. The committee's perceptions on causes of

rUTIs at the facility also influenced the implementation process. These suspected causes included:

- Improper assessment and identification of infection by the nursing staff.
- Inconsistencies in using a standardized criterion such as McGeer (Appendix A) for diagnosis
- Lack of adherence to evidence-based protocols by medical providers and nursing staff.

The DNP student and the infection control nurse conducted random audits to ensure both medical providers followed the agreed-upon guideline.

- Inappropriate UTI diagnosis and treatment with antibiotics during the hospital stay. The team and the DNP student took the lead on antibiotic surveillance; the DNP student confirmed if antibiotics were indicated.
- Inconsistent or inadequate hydration program. The committee developed a hydration program, which should be followed if not contradicted.
- Substandard peri-care techniques: Education on peri-care skills was provided to new nursing staff hired and re-evaluated every six months with the current team.

Institutional Review Board Approval

IRB approval was obtained through California State University, Los Angeles (CSULA) IRB before implementing the QI project. All protocols to ensure confidentiality was observed during data extraction. For example, the DNP student protected data confidentiality by keeping all project-related data secure in a locked file drawer and only available to the investigator, in addition to backup storage on a password-protected digital platform. Also, the study was carried out with utmost regard for the anonymity of the respondents. Only the project lead, an independent contractor at this facility, the DS nurse, and the DON had access to data. All

identifiers linked to the participants were redacted as indicated in the requirements exempt from category 2 (Appendix K). Further, the DNP student ensured that all participants were reminded that participation in the project was voluntary. All participants were informed of their right to opt out of the study should they feel uncomfortable.

Measures

As indicated earlier, professional development sessions targeting staff were implemented. The DNP student consulted an educational specialist to review the teaching materials and to lead face-to-face training sessions. Educational sessions were offered biweekly during the staff's shift hurdles. These in-person education sessions took place within the facility's conference room, often lasting 30-40 minutes (Appendix M). More specifically, the education sessions included the project introduction, core features of the revised guideline, and the implication strategies among the elderly population living in institutionalized facilities. The proposed clinical guideline was offered in all five nursing stations. At the end of every session, participants sought clarification and offered feedback regarding the evidence-based project. Participants were provided with educational materials to serve as constant reminders and ensure compliance with the newly developed UTI guideline. The revised guideline entailed assessment, prevention measures, proper collection of urinalysis specimens, and indications of when antibiotics should be prescribed.

Data was collected through Qualtrics, an online survey software, and follow-up phone calls. The DNP student obtained participants' demographic information before the start of the project. The demographic information was used to determine whether the individuals involved met the inclusion criteria. The DNP student also collected pre-implementation data on the rate of recurrent UTIs and post-test data on the rate of recurrent UTIs, primarily through follow-up

phone calls to the SNF administration. The data collection instruments allowed the participants to be differentiated based on demographic data such as age, gender, education, and experience. In addition, the survey included Likert scales and open-ended questions that were developed specifically for this project. Lastly, the survey was distributed through QR codes, ensuring participants responded once.

Results and Analysis

Sample Characteristics

The total number of participants that took the survey was 33 nurses. Participants were predominantly working full-time (78%) at the SNF. Most participants (58%) were between the ages of 18-35, 33% between ages 33-45, and 9% above age 45. Their level of education varied from technical school to master's level, with LVNs representing the largest proportion at 63%. The number of years of experience among participants varied. However, the mean was two years and a standard deviation of 1.04 (Appendix G).

Analysis

Most participants (56%) indicated using the McGeer UTI criteria (McGeer et al, 1991). In the open-ended response to the survey, participants reported implementing various recommendations in the McGeer protocol, including plenty of fluids, peri care, hydration, antibiotics, wiping from front to back, and using the restroom for continent patients. However, 18% of the participants indicated no experience utilizing the guideline, while 21% were unsure whether they had used it. Also, a comparative analysis of the McGeer UTI criteria and evidence-based practices (i.e., comparison of data from literature review and content of the McGeer criteria) revealed that the McGeer criteria do not include evidence-based practice preventative measures such as hydration, catheter management, hygiene, and the correct way of collecting a urine specimen.

In this project, 42.42% believe that the new guideline is adequate, 21.21% believe it is somewhat adequate, 9.09% believe it is neutral, 18.18% believe it is inadequate, and 9.09% believe it is extremely inadequate. Furthermore, 85.29% believe the new guideline is easy to use, while 14.71% believe it requires more clarity. On a scale of 10, half of the nurses rated the

guideline 10 out of 10, 3.59% rated it 9, 10.79% rated it 8, 7.14% rated it 7, and 10.71 rated it 6. However, 17.85% of nurses rated the guideline 5 and below. See Appendix H for staff perception of the proposed clinical guideline.

Pre and Post rUTI Rates

As demonstrated in Appendix I, there was a gradual change in the reported rUTI rates among the residents across the six months. During the first three months before project implementation (October-December), the average number of reported rUTI was 9.3 cases. However, across the final three months after implementation (January-March), the average number of reported rUTI was 8.6 cases. It is important to note that the sample size was too small to allow for statistical significance analysis. In terms of the SNF resident population, in October, there were 263 residents in November 271, December 267, January 270, February 266, and March 269.

Cost Analysis and Timeline

Total costs incurred with this QI project were minimal. All QI committee education meetings were held at no cost in the facilities conference room. The DNP student attended nurses' huddles at the beginning and end of the shift and engaged the nurses during breaks. The proposed clinical guideline education sessions served as a refresher course and in-service opportunity for the participants. The costs connected to the project were mainly around printing and laminating the proposed guideline, buying pins, and providing donuts and coffee to staff. The total cost incurred for the project was estimated to be \$158.47 (Appendix F).

IRB approval was received in December 2022, and the QI project was introduced in the same month to the nursing staff. Focused interviews and educational sessions occurred between the last week of December to the second week of January 2023. Electronic surveys were

officially published in the first week of February and were open for four weeks. Subsequently, data analysis and planning followed.

Nursing Staff Perception of the Effectiveness of the New Guideline

Most participants (56%) reported using the old guideline before the intervention, suggesting moderate use. However, most (63%) agreed that the revised guideline provided adequate information on preventing, assessing, and treating rUTIs. 36% did not rate the protocol as adequate. In addition, a notable majority (85%) reported that the revised guideline was easy to use. Similarly, 70% of the participants rated the revised protocol at a seven or above regarding the likelihood of future use.

Discussion

The primary purpose of this doctoral project was to identify and implement an evidence-based mechanism for reducing the rate of rUTI among geriatric residents in SNFs. This goal was achieved by conducting a systematic literature review and developing revised clinical guidelines to improve the prevention and treatment of rUTIs in SNF residents. Additionally, the project investigated the staff perceptions of the new proposed clinical guideline on avoiding and treating rUTIs in elderly residents in SNF settings. The key project questions for the project were (1) Do the assessment, prevention, and treatment measures reflect current evidence-based practices? (2) Do new guidelines reduce the rate of rUTIs among elderly residents in skilled care facilities? and (3) What is the nursing staff's perception of the effectiveness of the new guideline? Findings from the study showed that the assessment, prevention, and treatment measures at the SNF partially reflect evidence-based practices, given that they were based on the McGeer protocol (McGeer et al, 1991). A detailed literature review indicated that the McGeer protocol omits key evidence-based UTI management strategies. Notably, there was a slight but gradual change in the rates of reported rUTI among the residents across the six months of the data collection period. A comparison of rUTI rates between the first (October-December) and the last three months (January-March) indicates an average drop of 0.7 cases (9.3 to 8.6). Broadly, most of the nurses surveyed shared positive perceptions of the revised protocol.

The results of the project have important implications for nursing staff. However, the implications must be examined in light of the limitations discussed in the section below. First, the results indicate a slight reduction in rUTI rates among residents, particularly between October and March. The project design does not allow for a causal claim to be established. However, the reduction in rUTI rates appears to correlate with the intervention period. This

finding is not surprising since the revised protocol reflected evidence-based practices. Also, the finding suggests that further research is needed to ascertain any potential relationships between implementing the revised protocol and reducing rUTI rates. Additionally, whether the 0.7 reduction in UTI rates was clinically significant is still unclear. This is because the sample size for the study was too small to allow the researcher to calculate both statistical and practical significance. Perhaps with a larger sample size, future researchers can establish whether there are meaningful differences and that the changes have practical significance in clinical settings.

Secondly, most participants (63%) agreed that the revised guideline provided adequate information on preventing, assessing, and treating UTIs. In addition, most participants (85%) reported that the revised guideline was easy to use. These findings suggest strong positive perceptions of the revised protocol. This finding may give confidence to practitioners, especially trainers looking to implement novel UTI management systems based on the revised McGeer tool (McGeer et al, 1991). The positive perceptions likely suggest that nurses may find it easy to use the new tool. However, further investigations should be done with larger samples to determine if the positive perceptions hold among representative samples.

Recommendations

As indicated earlier, the following recommendations should be considered in light of the limitations of the project:

1. Nurses should implement the revised McGeer (McGeer et al, 1991) guideline with particular attention to the evidence-based components.
2. Nurses should collect data on the reported rates of rUTI and the interventions implemented to determine if the interventions are effective.

3. Nursing care facilities should provide adequate training on the use of effective evidence-based UTI management strategies and collect data to determine which components of the training were practical.
4. Conduct bi-weekly meetings where the management reiterates the factors often resulting in rUTI incidences.

Besides the four key recommendations, it is essential to note that the face-to-face education sessions utilized in the project could be conducted virtually. So nurses could stay in constant touch with the patients. Afterward, participants could be required to write brief reflections on implementing the protocols.

Similarly, it is also recommended that the mid and high-level management at the SNF should collaborate with other institutions with dedicated resources to address the spread of infectious diseases in situ to create capacity for in-service training. Institutions such as John Hopkins have resources for the prevention, mitigation, and treatment of rUTI within care settings (Johns Hopkins Medicine, 2023). The SNF stands to gain from the shared knowledge and practices from the specialized research, as well as the reciprocity the SNF can offer through the dual exchange of qualitative information on how to tackle rUTI in the SNF setting, as John Hopkins is already promoting a culture of collaborating with LTC networks.

Also, the facility management could benefit from real-time feedback loops to identify possible shortfalls in operational effectiveness. This recommendation is based on the finding that no effective feedback loops were created within the facility during project implementation. The real-time feedback looks may assist the facility in responding proactively before recurrent UTI rates rise. It is anticipated that such actions would reduce patient suffering and rates of hospitalizations and lower costs for both the facility and the taxpayers.

Lastly, long-term systemic changes are recommended, including forming working groups that meet regularly, collect data, and develop real-time interventions based on evidence-based protocols such as the McGeer. The systemic reforms would be helpful in facilities with high turnovers like the current one. Generally, the established systems are expected to function even when new staff are hired to replace the ones who exit.

Limitations of the Project

There are a few limitations to be noted. The first was the small sample size. It is unclear whether the participants constitute a representative sample of nursing staff at the facility. Thus, these findings do not generalize to the entire facility or other institutions. In addition, some of the SNF staffers' responses were in Spanish. While the DNP student could translate those responses using technology, the limitations of technology may inhibit the collection of accurate information. Lastly, the rUTI rates were based on nurses' reports. Likely, self-reported data may not be entirely accurate, thus, introducing a certain degree of error in the study. In an ideal setting, especially under different circumstances, the rUTI rates could be measured and recorded using independent sources.

Conclusion

This project aimed to identify ways to sustainably manage the prevalence of rUTIs within SNFs by introducing a new protocol incorporating the McGeer criteria (McGeer et al, 1991) and evidence-based prevention and treatment measures. The project revealed that the revised McGeer protocol might hold promise regarding reducing rUTI in SNFs. However, many challenges may hamper implementation, including the need to standardize training and lack of long-term system-level support. Future scholars and stakeholders can all build upon the current project taking into account the limitations highlighted above.

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Appendix A:
McGeer Criteria

<p>UTI in resident WITHOUT catheter (any previous catheter must have been discontinued at least 48 hours before symptoms began)</p>	<p>Criteria 1 and 2 MUST be present. Both criteria must be present:</p> <p>1. At least 1 of the following sub-criteria</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Acute dysuria or acute pain, swelling, or tenderness of the testes, epididymis, or prostate <input type="checkbox"/> Fever or leukocytosis <p>AND</p> <p>At least 1 of the following sub-criteria:</p> <p>Acute costovertebral angle pain or tenderness o</p> <p>Suprapubic pain</p> <p>Gross hematuria</p> <p>A new or marked increase in incontinence</p> <p>A new or substantial increase in urgency new or significant increase in frequency</p> <p>In the absence of fever or leukocytosis, then two or more of the following sub-criteria:</p> <p>Suprapubic pain</p> <p>Gross hematuria is a marked increase in an incontinent or marked increase in urge or marked increase in frequency.</p> <p>AND</p> <p>2. 1 of the following sub-criteria</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> At least 10^5 CFU/mL of no more than two species of microorganisms in a voided urine sample 	<p>UTI should be diagnosed when there are localizing genitourinary signs and symptoms and a positive urine culture result. A diagnosis of UTI can be made without localizing symptoms if a blood culture isolate is the same as the organism isolated from the urine and there is no alternate site of infection. In the absence of a clear alternate source of infection, fever, or rigors with a positive urine culture result in the non-catheterized resident or acute confusion in the catheterized resident will often be treated as UTI. However, evidence suggests that most of these episodes are likely not due to infection of a urinary source. Urine specimens for culture should be processed as soon as possible, preferably within 1–2 h. If urine specimens cannot be processed within 30 min of collection, they should be refrigerated. Refrigerated specimens should be cultured within 24h.</p>
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	<input type="checkbox"/> At least CFU CFU/mL of any number of organisms in a sparging and-out catheter	
<input type="checkbox"/> UTI in resident WITH catheter (If symptoms begin within 48 hours after discontinuing a catheter, count it as related to the catheter.	<p>Both criteria must be present: At least 1 of the following sub-criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Fever, rigors, or new-onset hypotension, with no alternate site of infection <input type="checkbox"/> Either acute change in mental status or acute functional decline, with no alternate infection <input type="checkbox"/> New-onset suprapubic pain or costovertebral angle pain or tenderness <input type="checkbox"/> Purulent discharge from around the catheter or acute pain, swelling, or tenderness of the testes, epididymis, or prostate <p>AND must have: Urinary catheter specimen culture with at least 10^5 CFU of any organism(s)</p>	<p>UTI should be diagnosed when there are localizing genitourinary signs and symptoms and a positive urine culture result. A diagnosis of UTI can be made without localizing symptoms if a blood culture isolate is the same as the organism isolated from the urine and there is no alternate site of infection. Without a clear alternate source of infections, fever, or rigors with a positive urine culture, the non-catheterized resident or acute confusion in the catheterized resident will often be treated as UTI. However, evidence suggests that most of these episodes are likely not due to infection of a urinary source.</p> <p>Recent catheter trauma, catheter obstruction, or new-onset hematuria help localize signs consistent with UTI but are not necessary for diagnosis.</p> <p>Urinary catheter specimens for culture should be collected following the catheter replacement (if the catheter rent, catheters er in place for >14 days).</p>

Appendix B

Author Revised Guidelines for Prevention of UTI

Revised UTI Clinical guideline for prevention and UTI surveillance in Elderly residents in SNFs

Hydration

Speech evaluation for; new admits at risk for dysphagia, residents with new onset of swallowing issues.

Dietitians to keep track of patients at risk of malnutrition and those with weight loss.

Water pitchers must be changed every 24 hours and replenished every 4 hours. (1000, 1400, 1800)

Catheter management

Indications of an indwelling catheter

Urinary retention or obstruction with written doctor's orders.

It was prolonged due to spine-related problems.

Contamination of Stage III or IV pressure ulcers with urine which has impeded healing, despite appropriate personal care for the incontinence.

Hospice, comfort care, or palliative care (Terminal illness or severe impairment makes positioning or clothing changes uncomfortable or is associated with intractable pain.)

Chronic indwelling urinary catheter on admission Must be evaluated for its appropriate use.

Indwelling Catheter care

Discontinue all catheters that do not meet the appropriate use.

Change indwelling catheters when their system has been compromised.

Only closed indwelling urinary drainage systems are to be used

Empty drainage back when full

Good perineal and catheter care every shift

Hygiene

Ensure the perineal area is clean and dry for all dependent residents.

Wash and wipe from front to back.

Wash the area with warm water and mild soap and pat dry (avoid bubble baths and statistically).

Change incontinence pads and briefs when soiled.

Collecting UA C&S Specimen

Step 1 Collect urine before antibiotics are given for best results.

Step 2 Determine if the patient had a catheter or not.

Catheter	Without catheter
If the Catheter is in place for less than two weeks, ok Collect from the sampling port only (not the drainage bag.) Catheter in place for two weeks or more; remove the old catheter and collect urine from the new catheter	- Provide good peri-care before urine collection. - Obtain a clean catch or midstream urine to avoid contamination. - If this is not possible, then obtain urine by:

	a) in and out catheterization b) freshly applied condom catheter for men
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McGeer UTI Surveillance

Must fulfill both 1 AND 2.

- 1. At least one of the following signs or symptoms
 - Acute dysuria or pain, swelling, or tenderness of testes, epididymis, or prostate
 - Fever or leukocytosis, and ≥ 1 of the following:
 - Acute costovertebral angle pain or tenderness
 - Suprapubic pain
 - Gross hematuria
 - New or marked increase in incontinence
 - New or marked increase in urgency
 - New or marked increase in frequency
 - If there is no fever or leukocytosis, then ≥ 2 of the following:
 - Suprapubic pain
 - Gross hematuria
 - New or marked increase in incontinence
 - New or marked increase in urgency
 - New or marked increase in frequency
- 2. At least one of the following microbiologic criteria
 - $\geq 10^5$ cfu/mL of no more than two species of organisms in a voided urine sample
 - $\geq 10^2$ cfu/mL of any organism(s) in a specimen collected by an

in-and-out catheter

Must fulfill both 1 AND 2.

- 1. At least one of the following signs or symptoms
 - Fever, rigors, or new-onset hypotension, with no alternate site of infection
 - Either an acute change in mental status or acute functional decline, with no alternate diagnosis and leukocytosis
 - New-onset suprapubic pain or costovertebral angle pain or tenderness
 - Purulent discharge from around the catheter or acute pain, swelling, or tenderness of the testes, epididymis, or prostate
 - 2. Urinary catheter specimen culture with $\geq 10^5$ cfu/mL of any organism(s)
- Adapted from (Stone et al., 2012)

Appendix C

The Iowa Model-Revised

The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care

Appendix D

Iowa Model Integration into the QI Project

Appendix E

Participants Demographics

Participants Demographics

Measures	Count	Percentages
Age		
18-35	18	55%
36-45	11	33%
46-55	1	3%
56-65	2	6%
Above 66	1	3%
Employees Status		
Full-time	26	79%
Part-time	2	6%
Per-diem	5	15%
Level of Education		
LVNS	18	55%
RNs/Associates	7	21%
Bachelor's Degree	6	18%
Master's Degree	2	6%
Experience with the McGeer guideline		
Definitely Not	6	18%
Probably Not	2	6%
Might or might Not	7	21%
Probably yes	5	15%
Definitely yes	13	39%
Years of work experience		
<2 years	6	18%
2-5years	9	27%
6-10years	10	30%
>10years	8	24%
Adequacy of the Proposed Guideline		
Inadequate	3	9%
Somewhat inadequate	6	18%
Neither (adequate/inadequate)	3	9%
Somewhat adequate	7	21%
Extremely adequate	14	42%
Is the proposed Guideline easy to use?		
Yes	29	88%
No	4	12%

Appendix F**Cost Analysis**

Supplies	Cost
Printing & Laminating	57.00\$
Pins	5.00\$
Starbucks Coffee (Cups, lids, coffee cream, sugar, stir sticks, and napkins included.)	60.00\$
Donuts	36.47\$
Total cost	158.47\$

Cost Analysis

Appendix G

Job Specifics

Appendix H

Nurses Feedback on Likelihood of Using the New Clinical Guideline

Appendix I

rUTI Rates

Appendix J

Level of Education

Appendix K

IRB Approval Letter

Office Memorandum

DATE: November 17, 2022

TO: Tailakh Ayman, RN, Ph. D

FROM: Karina Martinez

PROJECT TITLE: [1956533-1] The development and implementation of new clinical guidelines to prevent and treat of rUTIs in Skilled Nursing Facilities
REFERENCE #: 22-9X

SUBMISSION TYPE: New Project

ACTION: DETERMINATION OF EXEMPT STATUS

DECISION DATE: November 17, 2022

REVIEW CATEGORY: Exemption category #2(i)

Thank you for your submission of New Project materials for this project. The California State University,

Los Angeles (Cal State LA) IRB has determined that this project is EXEMPT FROM IRB REVIEW

according to federal regulations.

We will retain a copy of this correspondence within our records.

IF ANY CHANGES ARE MADE TO THE METHODS AND PROCEDURES DESCRIBED IN THIS

PROTOCOL, YOU MUST SUBMIT A MODIFICATION APPLICATION SO THAT THE PROJECT MAY BE

RE-EVALUATED FOR EXEMPTION FROM IRB REVIEW.

For any inquiries about this project, please use the Send Project Mail option on IRBNet to contact Karina Martinez. It allows us to keep all correspondence related to this project in one place, rather than scattered between IRBNet and emails. This letter has been electronically signed in accordance with all applicable regulations, and a copy is retained within California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State LA) IRB's record

Appendix L

Permission Granted to use Iowa Model

You have permission, as requested today, to review and/or reproduce *The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care*. Click the link below to open.

[The Iowa Model Revised \(2015\)](#)

Copyright is retained by University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics. **Permission is not granted for placing on the internet.**

Reference: Iowa Model Collaborative. (2017). Iowa model of evidence-based practice: Revisions and validation. *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing*, 14(3), 175-182.
doi:10.1111/wvn.12223

In written material, please add the following statement:

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Please contact UIHCNursingResearchandEBP@uiowa.edu or 319-384-9098 with questions.

Appendix M

Development and Training Program

Dear (Nursing staff),

I am conducting an evidenced based study on the development and implementation of new clinical guidelines to prevent and treat of rUTIs in Skilled Nursing Facilities. The purpose of the study to reduce the rate of rUTI among geriatric residents in SNFs. The project aims to address the prevalence of rUTIs, which is currently at 15% in this SNF facility. Educational sessions will be offered twice weekly during the nursing staff's shift huddles. Sessions will also be held virtually for the team who could not manage to attend the in-person training. The in-person education sessions will take place within the facility's conference room.

Approximate time research activities will take for one participant to complete their participation will be 20-30 minutes. Additionally, a total of four educational sessions will be offered for every Nursing supervisor, lasting 30-40 minutes, about 160 minutes outside their regular. The DNP student will use reinforcements, including a bulletin board, infographics, and checking with staff weekly. At the end of every session, participants will be allowed to seek clarification and offer feedback regarding the evidence-based project. Participants will also be provided with educational materials to serve as constant reminders. To participate in the study, you must be a full-time nursing staff who are direct employees of the nesting facility. Exclusion criteria include nursing staff who are either per time or those who are contracted through registries. If participants feel uncomfortable during the study, they are permitted to opt out of the study

Disclaimer

THIS PROJECT HAS BEEN DETERMINED TO BE EXEMPT FROM REVIEW AND APPROVAL BY THE CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LOS ANGELES INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD FOR THE PROTECTION OF HUMAN SUBJECTS IN RESEARCH

Contact information for questions

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